

Excess adsorption of biopolymers and lactose sugar on soft surfaces. Adsorption of β -lactoglobulin on various types of soft surfaces[†]

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Abstract : Excess adsorption (Γ_2^1) of β -lactoglobulin (β -lg) from aqueous solution onto surfaces of served soft solid powder have been measured at pH 6.5 and ionic strength 0.05 and at 28°C. Γ_2^1 in most cases increases with increase in bulk concentration C_2 of β -lg until at a critical value of C_2^m at the state of monolayer saturation. The values of Γ_2^m for the surfaces different soft surfaces stand in the order cellulose > tristearin > cholesterol > phosphatidyl choline > casein-fat mixture > stearic acid > lysolecithin. The affinities of β -lg for different soft surfaces in terms of standard free energy of adsorption $-\Delta G^\circ$ in kg per kg of powdered solid can be calculated using integrated forms of the Gibbs adsorption equation. $-\Delta G^\circ$ for monolayer adsorption for different soft powders are found to increase linearly with increasing values of Γ_2^m and the constant value of $\Delta G^\circ/\Gamma_2^m$ is equal to ΔG°_B in kJ per mole β -lg adsorbed at the interfaces. In few systems, Γ_2^1 exceeds Γ_2^m when $C_2 \gg C_2^m$ due to multilayer adsorption at the interface. Following thermodynamic approach, free energy of aggregation of β -lg at the interface forming multilayers have been calculated.

Adsorption isotherms of β -lg on powdered stearic acid in the presence of different neutral salts (NaCl, KCl, CaCl₂, Na₂SO₄ and KSCN) at pH 6.5 have been critically compared at pH 6.5. These isotherms have been also compared with the isotherms at β -lg at stearic acids at pH 4.0. The difference of results at pH 6.5 and 4.0 are due to the difference in surface charge of β -lg and stearic acids.

Keywords : Excess adsorption, soft surfaces, adsorption of β -lactoglobulin, standard free energy of adsorption, adsorption on stearic acid powder.

Introduction

Living systems contain three different biopolymers, proteins, nucleic acids and polysaccharides which remain in contact with aqueous solvent in the presence of various small solutes and inorganic salts. The biopolymers in contact with solvent may remain in insoluble or soluble forms but all of these polymers are extensively hydrated¹. The soluble biopolymers are found to possess abilities for significant adsorption on the surface of powdered rigid solids under different physico-chemical conditions. Bull^{2,3} as early as 1956, first studied the extents of adsorption of egg albumin and serum albumin on powdered glass par-

ticles of known surface area and indicated surface orientation of these proteins at the interface from maximum packing of these biopolymers. Subsequently, adsorption of bovine serum albumin, ribonuclease and many other proteins from aqueous solution onto the hard surfaces of various rigid solid powders have been examined⁴⁻¹¹. Attempts have been made to calculate affinities of the biopolymers for these surfaces using thermodynamic approaches¹²⁻¹⁴.

Chattoraj and co-workers¹⁵⁻¹⁷ have first shown that nucleic acids and other important groups of biopolymers are able to have adsorption interaction with hard pow-

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dered surfaces or glass, alumina, charcoal and metal under different physico-chemical conditions. The affinities related to DNA-surface adsorption interactions have been calculated from thermodynamic treatment.

There exists also many insoluble organic polymers and molecular aggregates, which behave as soft matters and in contact with water (or other liquids), may disperse as colloidal suspension¹⁸. Examples of these solids are organic colloids, liquid crystals, insoluble or denatured proteins surfactants forming micelle, cellulose, foams, gels, emulsions, micro-emulsions and granular materials. The shape, size and surface areas of these dispersed matters can easily alter with alteration of physical conditions of various types, such solid materials are termed as "soft condensed matters" or "soft matters" by de Gennes and others¹⁸⁻²¹ only recently. Physical features of such soft matters have also been discussed by de Gennes in his Nobel lecture¹⁸.

The hard solid particles used as adsorbents can reflect on the overall macroscopic behaviour of the material because molecules present in the hard solid are well organized in a crystal lattice with no change of pattern at any mesoscopic phase¹⁹.

The soft matters have common properties such as large number of degrees of freedom, weak interactions between structural elements, delicate balance between enthalpic and entropic contributions to the free energy. These properties lead to large thermal fluctuations, a wide variety of forms, sensitivity of equilibrium structures to external conditions, macroscopic softness and metastable states²¹.

Das and Chattoraj²² earlier studied adsorption of proteins on soft oil-water surfaces with many interesting results. Gani *et al.*^{11,15} and Halder *et al.*¹⁶ have also investigated adsorption behaviour of proteins and nucleic acids on the soft surfaces of cellulose; casein under different physico-chemical conditions. Recently Chattoraj *et al.*²³ have studied adsorption isotherms of milk protein β -lg with milk casein in the presence of various inorganic salts and urea and they have demonstrated that bulk water and protein compete significantly for excess adsorption process. They have also shown that lyotropic effect of various salts for such adsorption process on soft surfaces is only partly valid.

In the present paper, our results on the adsorption

interaction of β -lg on the soft surfaces of stearic acid, milk fat, fat-casein mixture, phosphatidyl choline, lysolecithin, cholesterol and cellulose will be presented. The results thus obtained will be critically compared with the adsorption interaction of β -lg on the hard charcoal and alumina surfaces.

Materials and methods

Globular protein β -lactoglobulin from bovine milk (Sigma) was used as adsorbate in all cases. Different surfaces used as adsorbents are chromatography grade alumina powder (BDH), charcoal (Sigma), cellulose (Himedia, Mumbai), cholesterol (CSIR Centre for Biochemicals), casein with fat (prepared in laboratory as described below), lysolecithin (Sigma), milk fat (locally called 'ghee' obtained from market), phosphatidylcholine (Sigma), received as gift from Professor Dipak Das, University of Connecticut, USA, tristearin (Sigma), palmitic acid (Sigma), stearic acid (Sigma). Milk was procured from market (brand name Metro Diary), calcium lactate was obtained from LOBA Chemicals, Mumbai.

Casein mixed with fat was prepared in the following way: Metro diary milk was allowed to boil. While boiling calcium lactate was added. Milk protein casein coagulate was formed. This casein coagulate (locally called 'Chhana') contains 3.0% fat as the milk contained that amount of fat (as per the knowledge from Metro diary brand). Now this chhana was washed and dried in a dryer at 60°C for 2 h ground in mortar and pestle to make fine powder. Inorganic salts like NaCl, CaCl₂, KCl, Na₂SO₄ and KSCN were used as neutral salts for the study of adsorption of β -lg on stearic acid. Only NaCl was used for adsorption of β -lactoglobulin on other surfaces mentioned earlier. Folin reagent was used in protein estimation by Lowry method²⁴. Double distilled water was used throughout the adsorption experiments.

Adsorption experiment

Stock solution of NaCl and other salts of appropriate ionic strength were prepared. Stock solution of β -lactoglobulin was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of it in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The average pH or solution measured with a digital pH meter was found to be 6.5. While considering adsorbents such as charcoal, alumina cellulose, cholesterol, fat free casein and casein mixed with fat content, adsorption were performed following

the same manner described our previous publications²³.

In each adsorption experiment, a fixed amount W of dry adsorbent was taken in a series of round bottomed conical flask. In each of these flasks, a fixed volume V of β -lg solution of molar concentration C_2^i was taken. The stoppered flask contains adsorbent and adsorbent were shaken for 24 h at 24°C. All flasks were then taken away from the shaker. The supernatants after centrifugation at 5000 rpm were spectroscopically examined to be free of any suspended particles of adsorbents. The molar concentration (C_2) of β -lg in the supernatant was determined by protein analysis method of Lowry *et al.*²⁴.

The extent of adsorption Γ_2^1 in moles of β -lg per kg of dry adsorbent at pH 6.5 and at 28°C was calculated²³ using eq. (1).

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \frac{(C_2^i - C_2) \cdot V^i}{1000} \quad (1)$$

Here V^i is the volume of β -lg solution in ml associated per kg of dry adsorbent²³. It is equal to V/w where w is the weight of β -lg in solution in the flask the error for the experimental value of C_2^i remains in between 5–10 percent. The moisture contents of the adsorbents were measured by either heating the powders at 105°C or keeping the powders in a desiccator containing concentrated H_2SO_4 for four days followed by weighing.

An experimental difficulty was observed for study of adsorption of β -lg on adsorbents such as powdered stearic acid (at pH 6.5), milk fat, phosphatidyl choline, lysolecithin at pH 6.5. Addition of those types of adsorbents in β -lg solution directly was found to form dispersion of the colloidal particles in aqueous media. These fine particles cannot be separated from solvent by centrifuging the suspension at very high speed for a long period of time. An alternative experimental method for the adsorption was used in these cases. A series of stoppered conical flasks (each of capacity 250 ml) containing fixed volume V^i (equal to 40 ml) of molar β -lg solution of concentration C_2^i were taken. The ionic strength and average pH of the solutions were 0.05 and 6.5, respectively.

Fixed amount (w) of an adsorbent was taken in clean dry small plastic tube attached with a lid. Definite volume of pure heptane was added in each tube containing adsorbent with closed lid and the mixture was shaken to

dissolve powdered adsorbent completely in heptane. The lid of the plastic tube containing heptane solution was opened and the tube plus lid thus separated were dropped into the conical flask containing solution of β -lg of aqueous concentration C_2^i . The conical flask was shaken gently for ten minutes so that all the contents from small plastic tube got mixed with the aqueous solution of the two phase system. The empty plastic tube and the attached lid open were now taken out from the conical flask (with the help of a long forcep). These are washed with minimum amount of pure heptane which was quantitatively transferred to the conical flask also. Heptane was also checked not to dissolve any plastic material within this short period of time. The conical flask was then stoppered and allowed to shake gently in a shaker for an hour at 28°C. The flasks were then taken out from the shaker. The stoppers were removed and the open flasks were kept undisturbed for 24 h allowing heptane to escape fully in open air by evaporation. The adsorbents were found to form as solid lump to float on the upper surface of the aqueous solution present in the conical flask.

The flasks after closing with stopper were gently shaken for 12 h in the shaker. After centrifugation of this suspension at 5000 rpm, the clear supernatant was found to be free from any adsorbent particles by spectrophotometric examination. No smell of heptane was found from the system. By the use of heptane in this manner, colloidal formation in the system was prevented so that quantitative estimation of β -lg concentration (C_2) in clean supernatant was carried out as stated earlier²³. Values of Γ_2^1 for these soft solids were calculated from the experimental values of C_2^i and C_2 , and V^i using eq. (1).

Excess adsorption

It has been pointed out by Chatteraj *et al.*²³ that the excess adsorption of solute adsorbate in aqueous solvent at constant molal concentration (m_2) of neutral salt can be quantitatively given in eq. (2).

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \frac{W^i}{1000} (m_2^i - m_2) \quad (2)$$

Here m_2^i and m_2 are equal to $1000 n_2^i/n_1^i$, $1000 n_2/n_1$, and the weight of solvent W^i is equal to $n_1^i M_1/n_1^i$. Here n_1^i and n_2^i are moles of solvent and solute respectively per

kg of adsorbent before adsorption and n_1 and n_2 stand for their values per kg after adsorption. W^t represents the molecular weight of solvent water (of molecular weight M_1) before adsorption per kg of solid. Inserting these values in eq. (2), one finds²⁵

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma_2^1 &= n_2^t - n_1^t \cdot \frac{n_2}{n_1} = -\left(n_1^t - n_2^t \cdot \frac{n_1}{n_2}\right) \cdot \frac{n_2}{n_1} \\ &= -\Gamma_1^2 \frac{n_2}{n_1}\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

Here Γ_1^2 stands for solvent excess per kg of adsorbent whose value can be calculated from values of Γ_2^1 and n_2/n_1 using eq. (4) since

$$\frac{n_2}{n_1} = \frac{m_2}{55.5} = \frac{X_2}{X_1} \cong \frac{C_2}{55.5}\quad (4)$$

X_1 and X_2 stands for bulk mole fractions of solvent and solute components. For dilute solutions, $m_2 \cong C_2$ and eq. (2) may be converted to the form of eq. (1), since W^t becomes approximately equal to V^t . Also, it has been pointed out earlier²⁵ that

$$n_1^t = n_1 + \Delta n_1\quad (5)$$

$$n_2^t = n_2 + \Delta n_2\quad (6)$$

Here Δn_1 and Δn_2 stand for moles of solvent and solute respectively bound per kg of powdered adsorbent. Inserting these relations²⁵ in eq. (3)

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma_2^1 &= \Delta n_2 - \Delta n_1 \frac{X_2}{X_1} \\ &\cong \Delta n_2 - \Delta n_1 \frac{C_2}{55.5}\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

If experimental values of Γ_2^1 varies linearly with C_2 in certain region of bulk concentrations of β -lg then absolute compositions of the surface bound phase Δn_1 and Δn_2 in moles of solvent and solute respectively bound per kg of powdered solids can be evaluated²⁵ from the slope and intercept of the plot. Further, when Γ_2^1 attains a maximum value Γ_2^m at a critical value C_2^m , Δn_1 value will be zero and the surface becomes free of adsorbed water and $\Gamma_2^m \cong \Delta n_2$ when value of Γ_2^m increases further at $C_2 \gg C_2^m$, Δn_1 still becomes zero and multilayer of biopolymers will be formed at the interface. On the other hand, if Δn_1 becomes positive after attainment of apparent maxi-

imum value of Γ_2^m at C_2^m , Γ_2^1 will decrease with increase of C_2 . Further, if Γ_2^1 vs C_2 plot is linear in this concentration region, one can calculate values of Δn_1 and Δn_2 using eq. (7) from the slope and intercept of the linear plot.

Results and discussion

In the living system, long chain saturated fatty acids such as stearic and palmitic acids in free form occur in small amounts. The number of carbon atoms in stearic and palmitic acids are 18 and 16 respectively. Critical micellar concentrations (CMC) for these acids are very low²⁶ so that even in dilute concentration range they may form micellar aggregates at pH 6.5. They adsorb water vapour and become hydrated²⁷. The pK value of these acids is 4.8 so that at pH 6.5 these are in anionic form. At pH 4.0, the long-chain stearic acid remains in unionized acid. These acids are insoluble below pH 4.8. Recently, Mitra *et al.*²⁸ have extensively studied adsorption or BSA on the surface of this unionized acid. Many interesting results were observed from thermodynamic analysis of the data at this acid pH.

At pH 6.5, surfaces of stearic acid particles may become partly ionized and sodium-stearate formed may remain also in small amount at pH 6.5, dissolved in aqueous solvent as soft micellar aggregate. However, particles of stearic acid are mostly in insoluble form. Actually, the solubility of stearic acid measured by radiotracer technique at pH 7.0 by Goodman²⁹ was indeed negligibly small. In the aqueous solution at pH 6.5, β -lg may bind with this trace amount of stearate ion. The protein may remain also adsorbed with insoluble and negatively charged particles of stearic acid. Stearic acid either at pH 4.0 or 6.5 behaves as soft matter since they are able to aggregate in colloidal form and are extensively hydrated²⁷. Protein in dissolved state at pH 6.5 may be imagined mostly to remain as negatively charged free biopolymer, since isoelectric pH of this milk protein is close to 5.0.

Isotherms for the adsorption of β -lactoglobulin on soft stearic acid particles at pH 6.5 and ionic strength 0.05 for different electrolytes (NaCl, KCl, Na_2SO_4 , CaCl_2 and KSCN) have been presented in Fig. 1. Γ_2^1 for β -lg in Fig. 1A in the presence of NaCl is observed to increase slowly as protein concentration C_2 is increased from zero until it reaches the maximum value Γ_2^m (vide Table 1) at a criti-

cal value C_2^m . When C_2 is increased further, Γ_2^m remains constant since fatty acid particle becomes apparently saturated with a monolayer of β -lg. However when $C_2 \gg C_2^m$, Γ_2^1 sharply increases from the value of Γ_2^m without approaching a limiting value. Protein in this state is assumed to form multilayers of β -lg on the surface of ionized soft stearic acid particles at pH 6.5 in the presence of NaCl. Similar types of isotherms for multilayer adsorption of BSA, β -lg and many other proteins on the unionized stearic acid surface at pH 4.0 have been observed by Mitra *et al.*²⁸ recently. For the adsorption of β -lg on unionized stearic acid particles Γ_2^m value at pH 4.0 is 5.0×10^{-5} moles β -lg/kg of stearic acid at $\mu = 0.05$. But at pH 6.5, Γ_2^m under same physico-chemical condition is 6.25×10^{-4} moles β -lg/kg of stearic acid (vide Table 1). This ten-fold increase in the value of Γ_2^m is surprising since β -lg itself is negatively charged above its isoelectric point 5.0. Probably at pH 6.5, the positive domain of β -lg undergoes strong attraction for soft surface of stearic acid particles containing slight negative charge.

In the presence of 0.05 M KCl the adsorption isotherm of β -lg on soft stearic acid particles has been presented in Fig. 1B. Here Γ_2^1 increases very slowly with increase of C_2 from zero to 1×10^{-5} (M) concentrations of protein indicating weak adsorption interactions between β -lg and charged stearic acid particles at pH 6.5. At higher values of C_2 , Γ_2^1 reaches the maximum value Γ_2^m which remains constant even when C_2 is considerably higher than C_2^m . This indicates absence of multilayer formation in this higher range of β -lg concentration on the soft surface of charged stearic acid particles. The affinity of β -lg for stearic acid in the monolayer is considerably higher than that between β -lg and β -lg forming multilayer at the interface.

The isotherms for adsorption of β -lg on charged stearic acid particle surface in the presence of CaCl_2 (vide Fig. 1C) are exactly similar to that observed in the presence of NaCl. Values of Γ_2^m for this system shown in Table 1 are observed to be considerably higher than that of NaCl possibly due to the significant binding of calcium ions to β -lg as well as on to the stearic acid surface. Multilayer formation has been found at higher values of C_2 exceeding C_2^m for CaCl_2 concentrations in agreement with that

observed²⁸ at pH 4.0.

The isotherm for adsorption of β -lg on ionized stearic acid particles in the presence of Na_2SO_4 is peculiar (vide Fig. 1D). Here Γ_2^1 increases with C_2 in the lower range of protein concentration and reaches a maximum value at a given value of C_2^m (vide Table 1). When C_2 exceeds C_2^m , Γ_2^1 value gradually decreases with increase of protein concentration and plot of Γ_2^1 against C_2 in this region is linear. From the slope and intercept of the linear plot the fixed values of Δn_1 and Δn_2 for water and β -lg bound to the ionized fatty acid surface in presence of Na_2SO_4 are 0.10×10^{-2} and 0.20×10^{-5} moles of β -lg and water per kg of the particles respectively (vide eq. 7). For NaCl, KCl, CaCl_2 at higher values of Γ_2^1 water bound to ionized stearic acid particles is zero due to the monolayer or multilayer coverage of the surface at higher values of C_2 as discussed earlier.

Water bound to ionized stearic acid particles is zero due to the monolayer or multilayer, coverage of the surface as discussed earlier.

In the presence of 0.05 (M) KSCN β -lg is extensively denatured²⁷. At lower values of C_2 , in the present of

Fig. 1. $\Gamma_2^1 - C_2$ plots for adsorption of β -lactoglobulin on stearic acid surfaces in the presence of various neutral salts at 28°C pH 6.5; ionic strength 0.05. (A) NaCl; (B) KCl; (C) CaCl_2 ; (D) Na_2SO_4 ; (E) KSCN.

Table 1. Adsorption affinities of β -lactoglobulin on stearic acid surface in presence of salts at pH 6.5 at 28°C and ionic strength of 0.05 M

Sl. no.	Salts	$\Gamma_2^m \times 10^3$ mole β -lg/kg stearic acid	$X_2^m \times 10^5$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ/kg stearic acid	$-\Delta G_B^\circ$ kg/mole β -lg
1.	NaCl	0.621	0.0162	0.088	42.9
2.	KCl	0.762	0.0288	0.026	37.9
3.	Na ₂ SO ₄	0.711	0.0135	0.025	35.7
4.	CaCl ₂	0.817	0.0157	0.100	38.2
5.	KSCN	1.80	0.049	0.052	34.8

KSCN, Γ_2^1 for adsorption or denatured β -lg on stearic acid particles is negative (Fig. 1E). But with increase of C_2 , Γ_2^1 becomes zero (at azeotropic state¹³) at a critical condition C_2^m . Γ_2^1 becomes zero at this state. When C_2 exceeds C_2^m , Γ_2^1 becomes positive. With further increase of C_2 , Γ_2^1 approaches a fixed value due to the formation of saturated monolayer of denatured β -lg at the ionized monolayer at a value C_2^m .

We thus find that the adsorption isotherms of β -lg on the surfaces of soft stearic acid particles in the presence of different inorganic salts are significantly different from each other as a result of the change of hydration of powdered fatty acid salts and proteins. Values of Γ_2^m for different neutral salts stand in the order KSCN > CaCl₂ > KCl > Na₂SO₄ > NaCl. This order partly agrees with Hofmeister series of electrolytes^{12,31} for biopolymer hydration observed for many systems¹.

In the adsorption isotherm of β -lg with soft surfaces of milk fat powder, Γ_2^1 is observed to increase with the increase of C_2 (vide Fig. 2B) until at a critical value C_2^m , Γ_2^1 reaches the maximum value Γ_2^m of protein equal to 1.01×10^{-3} moles per kg of fat (vide Table 2). Here fat contains different types of fatty acid derivatives which are heterogeneous in structure. Extent of adsorption β -lg on the soft surface of tristearin (containing same fatty acid derivative of stearic acid) as function of C_2 is also presented in Fig. 2A. The shape of the adsorption isotherms for milk fat and tristearin at lower range of C_2 are similar although at high values of β -lg concentrations, maximum value of adsorption for tristearin has not yet been attained. Also at a lower fixed value of C_2 , Γ_2^1 for tristearin is significantly larger than that of milk fat containing various types of fatty acid derivatives. We can thus conclude that extent of surface interaction of β -lg

with fat significantly depends on the type of derivatives of fatty acids in fat and possibly their arrangement in the soft organic compound.

In the case of preparation of casein from milk, about three percent of milk fat is associated with precipitated milk protein. The separated mixed precipitate can be dried and the powdered form of the material was kept in contact with soluble β -lg solution at pH 6.5 and $\mu = 0.05$ at 28°C for 24 h. Following experimental analysis, the values of Γ_2^1 of β -lg for the mixed fat-casein surface have been plotted with increasing value of C_2 (vide Fig. 3C). The values of Γ_2^1 for this system are slightly negative i.e. C_2^1 is less than C_2 at a given value of C_2 thus indicating excess of the water molecules complexed with casein-fat mixture. But at higher concentration range of C_2 , Γ_2^1 for these soft systems increases to positive value beyond azeotropic state and at C_2 equal to a critical value Γ_2^1 , Γ_2^m reaches the maximum value 0.72×10^{-3} moles per kg of powdered casein-fat mixture. For adsorption of β -lg on pure casein powder in the absence of fat, Γ_2^m is shown to be 0.91×10^{-3} moles of β -lg per kg of powdered solid²³.

In Figs. 2C and 3D, the isotherms for the adsorption of β -lg on the surface of soft powders of two phospholipid powders e.g. phosphatidyl choline and lysolecithin

Fig. 2. $\Gamma_2^1 - C_2$ plots for adsorption of β -lactoglobulin on different soft and hard surfaces at 28°C pH 6.5; 0.05 (M) NaCl concentration. (A) Tristearin; (B) milk fat casein mixture; (C) phosphatidylcholine; (D) charcoal.

Table 2. Adsorption affinities of β -lactoglobulin on soft and hard surfaces at pH 6.5, ionic strength (NaCl) 0.05 M and 28°C

Sl. no.	Soft particle	$\Gamma_2^m \times 10^3$ mole β -lg/kg soft material	$X_2^m \times 10^7$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ/kg adsorbent	$-\Delta G_B^\circ$ kg/mole β -lg
1.	Stearic acid	0.62	0.0016	0.088	42.9
2.	Lysolecithin	0.25	0.0380	0.140	48.2
3.	Phosphatidylcholine	1.02	0.0216	0.050	49.2
4.	Alumina	1.40	0.0216	0.064	49.3
5.	Charcoal	1.21	0.0205	0.057	49.5
6.	Tristearin	1.32	0.0157	0.068	49.9
7.	Casein fat mixture	0.72	0.0252	0.048	49.6
8.	Cellulose	1.12	0.0234	0.105	49.2
9.	Cholesterol	1.08	0.0270	0.053	49.1

respectively at pH 6.5, in presence of 0.05 NaCl at 28°C have been presented. Both the adsorbent contain glycerine whose two hydroxyl groups remain in esterified form with two fatty acid chains (one saturated and other unsaturated). The remaining hydroxyl group of glycerine is esterified with residue containing phosphatidyl choline and lysolecithin residues for phosphatidyl choline and lysolecithin respectively. It is found that β -lg undergoes significant adsorption interaction with both these lipids at high values of C_2 forming protein-lipid adsorption complexes. The saturation state for powdered phosphatidyl β -lg complex exists in the monolayer form on soft interfaces with complete removal of interfacial water. On the other hand lysolecithin containing free hydroxyl groups in their ionic phosphate residue adsorbs more water at low values of C_2 . Values of Γ_2^1 are also quite low in this concentration region. By assuming extended orientation at the interface of lysolecithin, surface water is removed with the formation of saturation protein layer on phospholipid surface at relatively low region of protein concentration. When $C_2 \gg C_2^m$, value of Γ_2^1 sharply increases without approaching limit indicating formation of protein multilayers on the soft surface of lysolecithin. Further, Γ_2^m for phosphatidylcholine is significantly higher than that for lysolecithin (vide Table 2) possibly due to entirely different orientation of the β -lg molecule on the protein packed monolayer on the two types lipid surfaces formed on the soft materials of phosphatidyl choline and lysolecithin.

Powdered cellulose and cholesterol respectively containing hydroxyl groups in their molecules and in contact

with aqueous solution, the insoluble materials of these organic compounds are extensively soft in nature. The adsorption isotherms of β -lg on the surfaces of these two powders are presented in Figs. 3A and 3B, Γ_2^1 for the adsorption of β -lg on cellulose increases with increase of β -lg concentration at low values of C_2 until at a critical value of C_2^m , the surface of the soft powder of cellulose appears to be saturated with β -lg. However, at higher values of C_2 exceeding C_2^m , Γ_2^1 increases sharply without limit forming multilayers of protein on the soft interface. Adsorption of β -lg on the cholesterol surface is regular one and at C_2 exceeding C_2^m , it attains maximum value Γ_2^m . Thus we have presented isotherms for adsorption of β -lg on various surfaces of organic soft materials and compared their monolayer saturation values Γ_2^m in Tables 1 and 2 expressed in terms of moles or β -lg adsorbed per kg of different soft materials as adsorbents.

In Figs. 2D and 3E, extents of adsorption isotherms of β -lg on the surfaces at rigid powdered materials of charcoal and alumina respectively have been presented. The monolayer values of β -lg on these hard powders per kg of rigid powder given in Table 2 are found to be of the comparable order of magnitude to those obtained for adsorption of this protein on different soft surfaces. Unlike soft particles, the surface areas of hard particles remain unchanged with alteration of C_2 , so that Γ_2^1 can be expressed in terms of extent of adsorption per unit surface area of these powders which can be measured from separate experiments³.

Affinities of adsorption interaction

From all these discussions so far made, the values of

Fig. 3. $\Gamma_2^1 - C_2$ plots for adsorption of β -lactoglobulin on different soft and hard surfaces. (A) Cellulose; (B) cholesterol; (C) casein fat mixture; (D) lysolecithin; (E) alumina.

maximum affinities Γ_2^m of β -lg per kg of powdered adsorbents stand in the order (vide Table 2), cellulose > alumina > charcoal > cholesterol > phosphatidyl choline > case in fat mixture > stearic acid > lysolecithin. This order is not dependent on hard or soft nature of the powdered substance used as adsorbents. The surface areas of hard surfaces remain fixed but for soft surfaces, the areas change with progress of adsorption.

Using integrated form of the Gibbs adsorption equation, standard free energy change ΔG° for the maximum adsorption of biopolymer per kg of powdered soft or hard material can be calculated^{13,25} using eq. (8).

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \int_0^{\Gamma_2^m} \frac{\Gamma_2^1}{X_2} dX_2 + RT \Gamma_2^m \ln X_2^m \quad (8)$$

Here the mole fraction X_2 is taken to be equal to $C_2/55.5$ (vide eq. 4) for dilute solution of biopolymer. The first term of the right side of eq. (8) represents the change of free energy when the mole fraction Γ_2^1 of the soluble biopolymer changed from zero to its constant value X_2^m (equal to $C_2^m/55.5$). The second term in eq. (8) stands for the free energy change as a result of alteration of the mole fraction of β -lg from X_2^m to unity by hypothetical dilution process^{13,25}. In Tables 1 and 2, values of $-\Delta G^\circ$

for different systems calculated from experimental data are presented. Values of ΔG° in Tables 1 and 2 are found to increase with increase in the maximum affinities Γ_2^m for different systems. Also when Γ_2^1/Γ_2^m is unity, the monolayer surface of the powdered solid is saturated. For Γ_2^1/Γ_2^m ratio less than unity, the adsorbed monolayer remains unsaturated. At a given value Γ_2^1/Γ_2^m , the apparent standard free energy change^{23,31}, ΔG_{app}° of the unsaturated monolayer can be calculated using eq. (9).

$$\Delta G_{app}^\circ = -RT \int_0^{\Gamma_2^1} \frac{\Gamma_2^1}{X_2} dX_2 + RT \Gamma_2^1 \ln X_2 \quad (9)$$

Values of ΔG_{app}° for unsaturated monolayers are found to vary linearly with Γ_2^1/Γ_2^m (vide Fig. 4) and the slope of the linear plot becomes equal to ΔG° observed for saturated monolayer. This indicates that the standard free energy change for saturated and unsaturated monolayers are same^{25,31}.

Fig. 4. Plot of ΔG_{app}° vs Γ_2^1/Γ_2^m for the adsorption of β -lactoglobulin on cellulose (A) and cholesterol (B) surfaces.

We have also observed that β -lg undergoes multilayer adsorption on stearic acid surfaces in the presence of NaCl and CaCl_2 (vide Fig. 1). Multilayer formation of β -lg on cellulose and lysolecithin surfaces in presence of NaCl

(Figs. 2 and 3) takes place on the cellulose and lysolecithin surfaces in the presence of NaCl at higher bulk concentration of protein. Values of ΔG_{app}^0 in these cases can also be calculated using eq. (9) at this high range of β -lg concentrations. These values of ΔG_{app}^0 vary linearly with $1/\sqrt{X_2}$ and the linear plot can be extrapolated to $X_2 = 1$ (vide Fig. 5 and Table 1 and Table 2) whereby values of standard free energy change ΔG_m^0 are evaluated at unit mole fraction which comes out from Fig. 5 as -0.30 and -0.34 kJ/kg of β -lg for adsorption on stearic acid in presence of NaCl and CaCl_2 respectively. Difference $\Delta G_m^0 - \Delta G^0$ stands for the free energy change due to the interfacial aggregation of protein molecules, which became -0.21 and -0.24 kJ/kg of β -lg at these interfaces of soft solids²³.

Fig. 5. Plot of ΔG_{app}^0 vs $(X_2)^{-1/2}$ at the high concentration region for the adsorption of β -lactoglobulin on cellulose surface in presence of different neutral salts. (A) NaCl and (B) CaCl_2 .

We also notice from Table 2 that values of ΔG^0 for all the surfaces of different soft solids increase with increase of Γ_2^m in a thermodynamic scale of unit activity ($X_2 = 1$). Further values of $\Delta G^0/\Gamma_2^m$ equal to ΔG_B^0 for the transfer of one mole of β -lg to the surface of these soft solid particles are close in magnitude so that average

values of ΔG_B^0 for adsorption of egg albumin and on hard glass powder BSA have been calculated in molar scale for the first time by Henry Bull^{2,3} using similar type of eq. (8) and to honour his name, the subscript *B* in ΔG_B^0 has been introduced¹³.

The close values of ΔG_B^0 in Tables 1 and 2 may further indicate that interaction of one mole of β -lg with a mole of active spot of surfaces of soft solid particles are approximately constant. The primarily attached molecules in the monolayer phase may then expand, orient according to its size and unfolding state of the adsorbate β -lg on the surface so that interfacial packing of the molecules per kg of the soft surface signified by the value of Γ_2^m will be widely different from each other at the state of saturation. For this reason, ΔG^0 equal to $(\Delta G_B^0 \cdot \Gamma_2^m)$ at the state surface saturation will be widely different from each other¹⁷.

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